

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON BEHAVIOR OF VINYL-ESTER/ GLASS COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Environmental effects on vinyl-ester glass composites has been measured on two types of composites: A) glass E plain woven fabric and gel-coat reinforced by C glass veil mat, vinyl ester resin Derakane 411-45 , B) C glass veil mat reinforced vinyl ester resin Derakane 411-45. Specimens for creep and impact tests have been immersed for 1000 h to distilled water and 5% aqueous solution of sulphuric acid with temperature 60°C. Two tests on the samples have been done: creep tests in tension and impact tests. During the creep tests the specimens have been subjected to a constant tensile load in special set-up constructed at Klokner Institute. Charpy impact tests have been done on the unnotched specimens in the flat-wise position using an instrumented pendulum hammer.

KEYWORDS: environmental effects, vinyl-ester, glass fibres, absorption, creep testing, impact testing, failure, damage.

INTRODUCTION

Composites consisting of vinyl-ester (VE) and glass (G) fibres are frequently used in corrosive environment. In addition to mechanical loads and temperature the composites are exposed to corrosive fluids which diffuse into the VE matrix and may also degrade the interface and glass fibres. The internal damage can occur as hydrolysis of VE matrix, micro-cracking and chemical etching of glass fibres. The presented paper was aimed to study the degradation processes in composites reinforced by glass fibers and vinyl-ester resins.

TESTING

Two types of composites were prepared in the form of the sheets by a wet lay-up method for creep and impact testing. VE resins from Dow Chemical Derakane 411-45 were used. The sheets were prepared as follows:

- A) seven layers of glass E plain woven fabric (weight 500 g/m²) with stacking sequence [0°] and gel-coat surface layers 0.4-0.6 mm thick, reinforced by C glass veil mat,
- B) resin Derakane 411-45, reinforced by C glass veil mat.

Specimens for creep and impact tests were cut from the sheets. Test specimens were of size for creep tests 15x 150 mm, for impact tests 10x 50 mm. The thickness was given by the thickness of the sheet (average 3-4 mm). The sheets have been immersed for 1000 h to distilled water and 5% aqueous solution of sulphuric acid with temperature 60°C. The long-term sorption of corrosive media into composite specimen A) and B) was evaluated.

One set of specimens was tested in original state after long-term (1000 h) storage at laboratory conditions (room temperature, 55% relative humidity). The second set was tested after a long-term immersion (as above).

The tensile tests have been conducted on specimens before and after exposition in corrosion media. The rate of loading was 1 mm.min^{-1} what corresponds to deformation rate $1\%.\text{min}^{-1}$.

Short-term tensile experiments were executed on 5 specimens for the identification of the ultimate tensile strength and modulus of the material. Results of initial tests are shown at tables 1-3, ultimate tensile strengths and strains after exposure in distilled water are shown in tab.4.

Table 1: Ultimate tensile strength and strain

	σ [MPa]	ϵ [-]
D 411-45 (C glass veil mat)	55.8	0.0308
D 411-45 (woven fabric,C)	330.8	0.0292

Table 2: Tensile modulus of Derakane 411-45 (C glass veil mat)

[MPa]	Strain ϵ [-]					
	0.000	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.010
Stress	1.82	6.92	12.5	18.2	23.9	29.4
Tang.mod.	2390	2680	2840	2880	2810	2660
Sec.mod.	2390	3460	3120	3030	2990	2940

Table 3: Tensile modulus of Derakane 411-45 (glass E plain woven fabric, C glass veil mat)

[MPa]	Strain ϵ [-]					
	0.000	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.010
Stress	7.92	29.0	51.9	75.9	100.0	125.0
Tang.mod.	9970	11100	11800	12200	12300	12200
Sec.mod.	9970	14500	13000	12700	12600	12500

Table 4: Ultimate tensile strength and strain (after exposure in distilled water)

	σ [MPa]	ϵ [-]
D 411-45 (C glass veil mat)	51.7	0.0287
D 411-45 (woven fabric,C)	214.1	0.0170

CREEP TESTS

Furthermore, the specimens have been subjected to constant tensile load in special set-up constructed at Klokner Institute, corresponding to stress levels 17.0 resp. 25.0 MPa. The specimens in the original stage and after exposure in distilled water or 5% aqueous solution of sulphuric acid have been tested. During the tests the specimen have been surrounded by distilled water or 5% aqueous solution of sulphuric acid at 60°C.

Fig.1: Experimental set-up

At the Fig.2 some results of creep tests on specimens from VE resin, case (B), are shown. The displacements were measured by LVDT sensors. The tests show significant changes in deformations already after 2 h loading. It has been proved that immersion in corrosion media accelerates creep. This phenomenon is caused by plasticization of matrix due to absorption of water from corrosive environment.

Fig.2: Creep test a) original, b) after exposure (distilled water)

IMPACT TESTS

Impact properties were determined by Charpy impact tests using a CEAST instrumented pendulum hammer. Initial hammer velocity was 2.9 m.s⁻¹ with maximal energy 15.4 J. Unnotched specimens were tested in the flat-wise position. The distance between the anvil

edges was 40 mm. The impact strength values and the ductility index (DI) were evaluated. DI is governed by the amount of energy absorbed during the propagation of the fracture. Significant changes of impact strength of model composite after exposure in 5% sulphuric acid and distilled water have been observed. Traces of load, absorbed energy and velocity of instrumented pendulum hammer have been calculated for both original and exposed vinyl-ester/glass composites (Fig.3). The load-displacement traces show that the composite has different failure behavior in original stage in contrast to exposed one. In original specimen most of the energy is absorbed during the initial stage of failure, whereas in the exposed specimen the main energy dissipation mechanism causes delamination during propagation phase of failure. This fact can be used in degradation assessment of composites. The results from both tests (creep and impact) affirmed that corrosion at hot distilled water is higher than corrosion at dilute sulphuric acid and is mainly caused by destruction of glass fiber/matrix interface due to hygrothermal action.

Fig.3: Load, energy and velocity–displacement traces
a) original, b)after exposure (distilled water)

CONCLUSION

The mechanical short term and long term properties of exposed composite specimens have been measured. The degradation due to hot distilled water has been found higher than to dilute sulphur acid. Effect of destruction of glass fibre/ matrix interface due to hygrothermal action of distilled water was observed.

Vinyl ester resins absorb water from corrosive environment and the shear strength of the laminate decreases due to plasticization of the matrix. As a consequence an extensive delamination during impact loading exposed composite based on Derakane 411-45 occurs.

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REFERENCES

1. Cerny, M., "Modeling of Degradation Processes in G/VE Composites", Proceedings of Internat. Conference on Composite Engineering (ICCE/5), Las Vegas, July 1998.
2. Cerny, M., Korinek Z., "Effect of Corrosive Environment on Properties of Vinyl-ester/Glass Laminates, Proceedings of 6th International AVK-TV Conference for Reinforced Plastics and Thermoset Moulding Compounds, Baden-Baden, October 2003.
3. Weitsman, Y.J., "Fluids Effects in Polymeric Composites – An Overview", Proceedings of the Conference "Progress in Durability Analysis of Composite Systems (Duracosys 97), Blacksburg, VA, September 1997